

SYNTHETIC MICROSCOPIC PLATELETS IMAGES GENERATION USING WGAN-GP

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Abstract

Introduction: Data scarcity presents a major challenge in medical imaging. Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) offer a promising solution by generating synthetic data to augment small datasets. **Aim:** The primary aim of this study is to evaluate the effectiveness of GAN-based synthetic data generation in enhancing CNN performance for platelet classification. **Methods:** The initial dataset contained 71 images, categorized into Control, Milrinone, and Zinc-plus-Milrinone classes. Using WGAN-GP, a synthetic dataset of 300 images was generated. These synthetic images were incorporated into the training of CNN models, including DenseNet121 and InceptionV3. Model performance was assessed comparing results from the original and augmented datasets. **Results:** In the non-augmented dataset, DenseNet121 achieved an accuracy of 81%, with 84% precision, 78% recall, and an F1-score of 81%. For InceptionV3, the non-augmented dataset yielded 82% accuracy, 80% precision, 76% recall, and an F1-score of 78%. However, after incorporating GAN-generated synthetic images, DenseNet121 achieved 97% accuracy, 97% precision, 95% recall, and a 96% F1-score, while InceptionV3 reached 94% accuracy, 93% precision, 90% recall, and 92% F1-score on the GAN-augmented dataset. **Discussion/Conclusion:** These results highlight the potential of GAN-generated synthetic data to significantly enhance the performance of CNN models in medical image classification, particularly in addressing the limitations of small datasets.

1. INTRODUCTION

Platelets, are the most important blood cells in haemostasis, being this an important skill on the body well-being maintenance [1,2,3]. Platelets are also known by the name of thrombocytes, have a diameter of 2-4 μm in diameter, and beside small are anucleate. They form aggregates which adhere to damaged vessel surfaces, becoming activated, and transforming into sticky plugs that culminate in thrombus formation which stop the bleeding process [4,5]. Beyond this physical role, platelets are regulated by intricate biochemical pathways, being one of the substances Zinc able to influence this process [5] [6]. Contrarily to red and white blood cells which are more studied not much attention has been placed in precise identification of platelet morphology and function. However, this is vital for diagnosing haematological disorders, as irregularities in shape or behaviour may signal defective function and underlying pathologies [7,8,9,10]. Traditional platelet classification relies on manual microscopic examination, a process prone to interobserver variability and subjectivity, beside very labour intensive [2,11,12]. Automating blood analysis to enhance efficiency and reduce human error is then of extreme importance [13,14], being this true also for platelets. Artificial Intelligence (AI), with the Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL), can be revolutionary in this task by enabling rapid, accurate and fully automatic analysis of microscopy images with low error margin [15,16]. DL techniques, such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), have shown great success in tumour detection, blood cell classification, phenotyping and in other medical imaging tasks, offering high performance solutions for classification, segmentation, and image quality enhancement [17,18,19,20]. Recent studies with CNNs application on classification of aggregates by agonist type and by phenotype morphological changes induced by treatments, demonstrate the potential of DL to automate and refine this field of platelets research [2,5,21]. However, to train the models needed for this research high quality, labelled platelet image datasets become imperative [22]. Datasets augmentation is a regular task of data processing for AI application, where rotations, scaling, and flips of the images are implemented for creating enlarged datasets [23]. Looking into the potentialities of AI for this research field it is possible to see that beside creating the challenge it can also provide the solution. In recent years, generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) have emerged as a transformative approach by synthesizing realistic images to expand datasets [24]. When applied to train AI models GAN based augmentation has improved classification accuracy in applications like liver lesion detection and chest X-ray analysis, suggesting its potential for platelet studies [25,26]. Recent research has explored custom CNN architectures and transfer learning to segment and classify blood cells, including platelets, with models designed to identify morphological changes induced by treatments such as zinc, milrinone, or their combination [5,21]. To address datasets limitations and advance platelet classification, this study compared a Wasserstein GAN with Gradient Penalty (WGAN-GP) generated dataset against traditionally augmented datasets. The performance of eight pre-trained CNNs (DenseNet121, DenseNet169, DenseNet201, VGG16, VGG19, InceptionV3, Inception-ResNetV2, and AlexNet) and two custom CNNs was evaluated using accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score across original, augmented, and GAN-based synthetic datasets. The objective was to determine whether GAN augmentation enhances classification accuracy and generalizability beyond traditional methods, while also exploring

AI's broader potential to decode platelet morphology and signalling in health and disease.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Data description

An initial dataset of 71 platelet images was used, categorized into three classes: Control (47 images), Milrinone (14 images), and Zinc plus Milrinone (10 images), as described by Abidoeye et al. [27].

Figure 1. Sample Images from the Platelet Dataset of each class (a) Control, (b) Milrinone, (c) Zinc plus Milrinone respectively.

This small dataset size presented challenges for training deep neural networks, motivating our augmentation strategies.

2.2. Data preparation and augmentation

The original dataset gave origin to three different ones: two augmented datasets but the traditional techniques and are identified as augmentation Level 1 and Level 2 and one synthetic dataset, created by application of a WGAN-GP. The creation process of these datasets is described with more detail below:

- Level 1 (141 images): Used random oversampling and basic images transformations (flips, rotation, zoom).
- Level 2 (1,463 images): Employed more extensive images transformations (shearing, additional rotation, and zoom ranges) to ensure a much larger dataset.
- Synthetic dataset (300 images): Generated using a WGAN-GP, thereby further expanding the available data for model training and classification.

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Each dataset was then divided into training (70%) and validation (30%) sets.

2.3. Transfer learning models

Eight pre-trained CNNs with ImageNet weights were finetuned for this task:

- DenseNet121, DenseNet169, DenseNet201 [28]
- VGG16, VGG19 [29]
- InceptionV3 [30]
- InceptionResNetV2 [30]
- AlexNet [31]

Each model's final layers were adjusted for three classes classification. Additionally, two custom CNNs were designed:

- Custom Model 1: Incorporating Conv2D, BatchNormalization, MaxPooling, Dropout, and two Dense layers.
- Custom Model 2: A simpler architecture with Conv2D and MaxPooling, followed by a single Dense layer.

2.4. GAN data augmentation or GAN data generation

The used WGAN-GP employed to generate synthetic platelet images is illustrated in Figure 2. This method was chosen due to its ability to address stability issues commonly encountered in traditional GAN training by utilizing the Wasserstein distance with a gradient penalty to enforce Lipschitz continuity [32,33].

1. **Generator:** This network transforms a latent noise vector into high-resolution (128×128 or 256×256 pixels) synthetic images using transpose convolutions, batch normalization, and LeakyReLU activations to ensure realistic feature generation.
2. **Critic (Discriminator):** The discriminator evaluates both real and generated images through convolutional layers, outputting a scalar "realness" score to guide the generator's improvement. To maintain training stability, the critic undergoes multiple updates per generator update before reaching convergence.

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GAN training was conducted over 5000 epochs per class (batch size = 128), generating 100 synthetic images per class. These synthetic images were integrated into the dataset and subjected to the same CNN training and evaluation pipeline as the other augmented datasets, enabling direct performance comparisons across augmentation methods.

Figure 2. WGAN-GP architecture for synthetic platelet image generation. The generator (top) produces synthetic images, while the discriminator (bottom) evaluates real vs. generated images to refine quality.

2.5. Model training and evaluation

2.5.1. Model training

All CNN models were trained for 100 epochs using:

Optimizer: Adam with a learning rate of 0.001.

Batch Size: 32 (128 tested in some trials).

Loss Function: Categorical cross-entropy for the multi-class classification.

Hyperparameters were tuned for optimal performance. The best-performing checkpoints were saved.

2.5.2. Evaluation metrics

The evaluation metrics used were:

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (1)$$

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (2)$$

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \quad (3)$$

$$F1Score = 2 * \frac{(Precision * Recall)}{(Precision + Recall)} \quad (4)$$

Confusion matrices, accuracy and loss plots were generated to visualize classification performance.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Classification results with the original dataset of 71 images

As shown in Table 1, the limited size of the original dataset resulted in moderate model performance. DenseNet121 achieved the highest accuracy at 81%, with a precision of 84%, while other architectures like DenseNet201 and DenseNet169 followed with 76% and 71% accuracy, respectively. However, VGG19 struggled, attaining only 52% accuracy, and the two custom CNN models underperformed significantly, particularly Custom Model 2, which had a precision of only 33%. These results highlight the challenge of training deep learning models with small datasets, reinforcing the need for data augmentation to improve generalizability.

Models (Batch size 32)	Accuracy (%)	F1-Score (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)
Custom Model 1	62	56	68	62
Custom Model 2	57	42	33	57
DenseNet121	81	79	84	81
DenseNet169	71	67	77	71
DenseNet201	76	74	83	76
VGG16	57	47	43	57
VGG19	52	45	40	52

VGG19-FF	62	59	63	62
InceptionV3	62	51	46	62
InceptionResNetV2	71	69	76	71
AlexNet	62	56	59	62

Table 1. Classification results with the original dataset of 71 Images for the different classification models with the metrics: accuracy, F1-score, precision and recall.

3.2. Classification results with the augmented dataset level 1 of 141 images

As presented in Table 2, performance improved across most architectures compared to the original dataset. DenseNet201 achieved the highest accuracy at 86%, followed by DenseNet121, DenseNet169, and InceptionV3, which ranged between 79% and 76%. The application of augmentation techniques contributed to enhanced model generalizability. However, Custom Model 2 exhibited significantly lower performance, with an accuracy of only 38% and a precision of 15%, indicating its limited capacity to learn from the expanded dataset.

Models (Batch size 32)	Accuracy (%)	F1-Score (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)
Custom Model 1	67	66	69	67
Custom Model 2	38	21	15	38
DenseNet121	79	79	79	79
DenseNet169	79	78	83	79
DenseNet201	86	86	88	86
VGG16	62	62	72	62
VGG19	64	64	68	64
VGG19-FF	76	76	80	76
InceptionV3	76	76	79	76
InceptionResNetV2	71	69	80	71
AlexNet	67	65	66	67

Table 2. Classification results with the traditionally augmented dataset of images, where was performed the Level 1 augmentation (141 images), for the different classification models with the metrics: accuracy, F1-score, precision and recall.

3.3. Classification results with the augmented dataset level 2 of 1,463 images

A substantial jump in performance was observed with the dataset augmented to the level 2, as shown in Table 3. In these experiments InceptionV3 and InceptionResNetV2 reached 99% accuracy with equally high precision and recall, underscoring the importance of a sufficiently

large, varied dataset. DenseNet201 with a 98% value of accuracy also performed exceptionally.

Models (Batch size 32)	Accuracy (%)	F1-Score (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)
Custom Model 1	97	97	97	97
Custom Model 2	88	87	91	88
DenseNet121	97	97	98	97
DenseNet169	97	97	97	97
DenseNet201	98	98	98	98
VGG16	97	97	97	97
VGG19	94	94	94	94
VGG19-FF	95	95	95	95
InceptionV3	99	99	99	99
InceptionResNetV2	99	99	99	99
AlexNet	30	14	9	30

Table 3. Classification results with the traditionally augmented dataset of images, where was performed the Level 2 augmentation (1,463 images), for the different classification models with the metrics: accuracy, F1-score, precision and recall.

3.4. Classification results with the synthetic dataset of 300 Images created by WGAN-GP

GAN-based augmentation, or synthetic data created by the WGAN-GP further enhanced classification outcomes, as shown in Table 4. DenseNet121 and Custom Model 1 both achieved 97% accuracy, while Inception-based models and DenseNet169 also scored above 90%. Although AlexNet improved slightly (74% accuracy), it still lagged behind more modern architectures.

Models (Batch size 32)	Accuracy (%)	F1-Score (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)
Custom Model 1	97	94	95	94
Custom Model 2	87	87	87	87
DenseNet121	97	97	97	97
DenseNet169	91	91	93	91
DenseNet201	96	96	96	96
VGG16	83	83	85	83
VGG19	89	89	89	89
VGG19-FF	88	88	89	88
InceptionV3	94	94	95	94
InceptionResNetV2	90	90	90	90
AlexNet	74	75	75	74

Table 4. Classification results with the synthetic dataset with 300 Images created by the WGAN-GP for the different classification models with the metrics: accuracy, F1-score, precision and recall.

3.5. Examples of the synthetic images created by WGAN-GP

Figure 3 illustrates the differences between the original dataset and the various augmentation strategies applied to platelet images. The first column has images of the different classes from the the original dataset, followed by images of the traditionally augmented to the Level 1 dataset, where were applied abasic transformations such as flipping and rotation. The third column showcases images from the traditionally augmented Level 2 dataset, incorporating more extensive modifications such as shearing and zooming. Finally, the last column presents images generated using a Wasserstein GAN with Gradient Penalty (WGAN-GP), producing synthetic platelet images that expand the dataset. The progressive transformations highlight the role of each augmentation technique in enhancing dataset diversity and model robustness.

Data Set	Original	Traditionally Augmented 1	Traditionally Augmented 2	WGAN-GP
Control				
Milrinone				
Zinc Plus Milrinone				

Figure 3. Comparison of original, traditionally augmented, and GAN-generated platelet images. From left to right: Original dataset, Level 1 augmentation, Level 2 augmentation, and WGAN-GP generated images.

4. DISCUSSION

The methodological choices in this study, particularly concerning data augmentation and model selection, significantly influenced the results obtained. The original dataset, consisting of only 71 platelet images, presented a considerable limitation for training deep learning models, leading to suboptimal performance due to overfitting. As observed in previous studies, deep learning models require large and diverse datasets to generalize effectively, and small sample sizes often lead to performance degradation [23,34]. In this study, models trained solely on the original dataset demonstrated moderate performance, with DenseNet121 achieving the highest accuracy at 81%, while simpler architectures such as VGG19 and AlexNet performed significantly worse, with 52% and 62% accuracy, respectively. These findings align with previous work in medical image classification, where small datasets have been shown to negatively impact deep learning models, particularly those with complex architectures [23,34].

To mitigate this issue, two levels of traditional augmentation were applied. The first level (141 images) employed basic transformations such as flipping, rotation, and zooming, whereas the second level (1,463 images) incorporated more extensive modifications, including shearing and additional rotation angles. As reported in Perez et al. [23], data augmentation has been widely acknowledged as a key strategy to mitigate overfitting and improve model robustness in deep learning applications. In line with these findings, the results of this study demonstrated that Level 2 augmentation significantly improved model performance, particularly for deeper architectures. Models such as InceptionV3 and InceptionResNetV2 achieved 99% accuracy, reinforcing existing literature, which suggests that large, diverse datasets enable deep networks to extract more representative features, ultimately leading to superior classification performance [32].

Further improvements were observed with GAN-based augmentation, where a WGAN-GP model generated 300 synthetic platelet images after being trained for 5000 epochs per class. As seen in Yi et al. [24] and Frid-Adar et al. [25], GAN-generated data has been shown to effectively enhance deep learning models, particularly in medical imaging applications where data availability is limited. The introduction of synthetic images further improved classification outcomes, with DenseNet121 and Custom Model 1 achieving 97% accuracy, demonstrating the effectiveness of synthetic data generation in complementing real datasets. However, it is important to note that while GAN-based augmentation provided substantial improvements, certain challenges remain. Prior studies have reported that GANs can suffer from mode collapse, where the model generates highly similar images, leading to a lack of diversity in the dataset [24]. In this study, the use of WGAN-GP helped mitigate this issue by ensuring more stable training and realistic image generation.

Comparative analysis of augmentation techniques indicates that traditional augmentation provided a strong foundation for improving model generalizability, but further enhanced classification accuracy has been achieved with the GAN-based augmentation by introducing synthetic variations.

The expectation was that augmentation would improve model robustness, particularly for deeper architectures, and the results support this hypothesis, but the degree of improvement

varied across models. Some results were somewhat unexpected, as the one of AlexNet's accuracy declining significantly to 30% on Level 2 augmentation, suggesting that its limited capacity for complex feature extraction made it less effective when trained on a highly varied dataset. Contrarily to AlexNet, DenseNet and Inception-based models exhibited substantial performance gains, this differences align with findings in Sandfort et al. which highlighted that deeper networks require larger and more diverse datasets to optimize feature extraction and classification [22]. These results further support the broader consensus in the literature that data augmentation plays a pivotal role in improving model generalizability, mitigating overfitting, and addressing dataset limitations in deep learning applications. As demonstrated in previous studies, including those on liver lesion classification, chest Xray diagnostics, and histopathology image analysis, augmentation techniques have consistently led to performance improvements across various medical imaging tasks [23,22,25]. Future research should investigate conditional GANs and domain adaptation strategies to enhance data augmentation, improving the diversity and quality of training samples. Additionally, transformer-based architectures should be explored for classification after augmentation, as they have recently shown strong performance in complex image classification tasks. Additionally, expanding the dataset with realworld platelet images and incorporating more sophisticated augmentation strategies, such as adaptive augmentation and metlearning approaches, may further enhance the generalizability and robustness of platelet classification models.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This study investigated platelet image classification using traditional data augmentation (Levels 1 and 2) and a WGAN-GP approach to generate synthetic data. Results showed that extensively augmented datasets (Level 2) and GAN-augmented data both significantly improved classification accuracy for advanced CNN architectures (particularly DenseNet and Inception families). These outcomes underscore the value of combining comprehensive augmentation strategies with GAN-based synthetic images, especially in cases where medical image data is limited.

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